

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Note on Double Aboodh Transform of Fractional Order and its Properties

S. Alfaqeh¹ and T. Özis²

¹Faculty of Science Department of Mathematics, 35100, Ege University, Bornova, Izmir, Turkey

²Faculty of Science Department of Mathematics, 35100, Ege University, Bornova, Izmir, Turkey

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR: S. Alfaqeh (sfaqeh@yahoo.com)

Abstract

In this study, we introduce definitions of a fractional double Aboodh transform of order α , where $\alpha \in [0, 1]$, for functions which are fractional differentiable. We then establish some main properties of this transform. Furthermore, we prove some related theorems.

Keywords: Fractional Laplace transform, Summudu transform, double Aboodh transform, Mittag leffler function

Mathematics Subject Classification: 26A33, 44Axx, 00A69

1 Introduction

Integral transform method is one of the most known method for solving partial differential equations of integer and fractional order. In literature, there are various integral transforms like Fourier [1], Natural[2,9], Laplace [3,4], Summudu [5,6], Aboodh [7,8] and so on. These transforms are used in physics, statistics and also in engineering. Double Laplace transform, double Summudu transform and double Aboodh transform were used to solve differential, integral equation and system of differential equation. Aboodh transform first introduced by Khalid Aboodh in 2013 is a transform derived from Fourier integral which is an efficient method to solve partial differential equations. Aboodh introduced a higher version called double Aboodh transform to solve linear partial, fractional and partial integro-differential equations. S. Alfaqeh, T. Ozis in 2019 [10] introduced the first Aboodh transform of fractional order and its properties [10]. The objective of the present Article is to define the fractional Double Aboodh transform and to present several main properties and theorems.

This study has been organized as follows: In section 2, we recall some definitions and results related to double Aboodh transform, in section 3, we introduce the definition of fractional double Aboodh transform. In section 4, we present and prove some properties of fractional double Aboodh transform, in section 5; we state the convolution theorem of the fractional double Aboodh transform and its proof. The inversion formula and inversion theorem and its proof of the fractional double Aboodh transform are given in section 6 and 7. Finally, the conclusion follows in section 8.

2 Preliminaries

In this section, we recall the definitions of double Aboodh transform, first fractional Aboodh transform, and the fractional derivative via fractional difference.

Definition 2.1. *let f be a continuous function of two variables, then the double Aboodh transform of $f(x, t)$ is defined by:*

$$A_{xt}[f(x, t)] = k(p, q) = \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} e^{-px} e^{-qt} f(x, t) dx dt, x, t > 0. \quad (1)$$

And,

$$f(x, t) = A_{xt}^{-1}[k(p, q)] = \frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\beta-i\infty}^{\beta+i\infty} p e^{px} \left[\frac{1}{2\pi i} \int_{\mu-i\infty}^{\mu+i\infty} q e^{qt} k(p, q) dq \right] dp, \quad (2)$$

EMAIL ADDRESS, S. Alfaqeh: sfaqeh@yahoo.com

EMAIL ADDRESS, T. Özis: turgut.ozis@ege.edu.tr

is the inverse of double Aboodh transform . For more details see [16].

Definition 2.2 (Fractional Derivative via Fractional Difference). Let $f(x)$ be a continuous function operator $FW(h)$ as following:

$$\Delta^\alpha f(x) = (FW - h)^\alpha f(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^j \binom{\alpha}{j} f(\gamma + (\alpha - k)h), \quad (3)$$

where h is a positive real number and denote a constant discretization span. Then the fractional difference of order α , $\alpha < 1$ of $f(x)$ is defined by

$$\Delta^\alpha f(x) = (FW - h)^\alpha = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} (-1)^j (j^\alpha) f(\gamma + (\alpha - k)h), \quad (4)$$

and its α -derivative is defined by

$$f^\alpha(x) = \lim_{h \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta^\alpha f(x)}{h^\alpha}. \quad (5)$$

For more details see [11,12].

Definition 2.3 (Modified Fractional Riemann-Liouville Derivative). Let $f(x)$ be the function that defined in definition 2.2, then

(a) If $f(x) = c$, where c is constant, then its α -derivative of order α is given by

$$D_x^\alpha f(x) = \begin{cases} \frac{c}{\Gamma(1-\alpha)x^\alpha}, & \alpha \leq 0 \\ 0, & 0 \end{cases}$$

(b) If $f(x)$ is not constant, hence

$$f(x) = f(0) + (f(x) - f(0))$$

With fractional derivative given by

$$f^\alpha(x) = D_x^\alpha f(0) + D_x^\alpha (f(x) - f(0)),$$

for $\alpha > 0$, we will put

$$D_x^\alpha (f(x) - f(0)) = D_x^\alpha f(x) = D_x (f^{\alpha-1}(x)).$$

If, $k < \alpha < k + 1$, we will put

$$f^\alpha(x) = (f^{\alpha-k}(x))^k, k \leq \alpha \leq k + 1, k \geq 1.$$

Theorem 2.1. The solution of fractional differential equation $dy = f(x)(dx)^\alpha$, $x > 0, y(0) = 0$, is defined by:

$$\begin{aligned} y(x) &= \int_0^x f(u)(du)^\alpha, \quad y(0) = 0 \\ &= \alpha \int_0^x (x-u)^{\alpha-1} f(u) du \quad 0 < \alpha < 1, \end{aligned}$$

where the integration is taken with respect to $(dx)^\alpha$.

For more result see [13,14].

Definition 2.4 ([17]). The Mittag-Leffler function is defined by

$$E_\alpha(x) = \sum_{j=0}^{\infty} \frac{x^j}{\Gamma(\alpha j + 1)}, \quad x \in \mathbb{C}, \Re(\alpha) > 0. \quad (6)$$

Definition 2.5 ([10]). The fractional Aboodh transform of function $f(x)$ is given by

$$A_\alpha[f(x)] = K_\alpha(P) = \frac{1}{p} \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-px)^\alpha f(x)(dx)^\alpha, \quad p \in \mathbb{C}, x > 0. \quad (7)$$

Definition 2.6 ([17]). The fractional double Laplace transform of function $f(x,y)$ is given by

$$F_\alpha^2(p,q) = \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px+qt)^\alpha) f(x,t)(dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha, \quad p, q \in \mathbb{C}. \quad (8)$$

3 Double Aboodh Transform of Fractional Order

The next definition characterizes the Double Aboodh transform of fractional order.

Definition 3.1. Let $f(x, t)$ be a function where $x, t > 0$, then the Double Aboodh transform of fractional order α is defined by

$$\begin{aligned} A_\alpha^2(f(x, y)) &= K_\alpha(p, q) = \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px + qt)^\alpha) f(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha, \\ &= \lim_{V, R \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^V \int_0^R E_\alpha(-(px + qt)^\alpha) f(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha, \quad p, q \in \mathbb{C}. \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

By using the property of Mittag-Leffler function (9) can be written as:

$$A_\alpha^2(f(x, y)) = K_\alpha(p, q) = \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px)^\alpha) E_\alpha(-(qt)^\alpha) f(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha. \quad (10)$$

Remark 3.1. When $\alpha = 1$, Fractional double Aboodh transform (9) turns to Double Aboodh transform (1).

Remark 3.2. From definition (9), $K_\alpha(p, 0) = K_\alpha(p)$, $K_\alpha(0, q) = K_\alpha(q)$, where $K_\alpha(\cdot)$, denote the fractional Aboodh transform given by equation (7).

4 Properties Of fractional double Aboodh transform

4.1 Linearity property

Theorem 4.1. Let $f(x, t)$, $g(x, t)$ be two functions, then:

$$A_\alpha^2\{a f(x, t) + b g(x, t)\} = a A_\alpha^2\{f(x, t)\} + b A_\alpha^2\{g(x, t)\},$$

where a, b are constants.

Proof. By applying the definition of fractional Aboodh transform, we can simply get the proof. \square

4.2 Changing of scale

Theorem 4.2. If $A_\alpha^2\{g(x, t)\} = k_\alpha(p, q)$, then

$$A_\alpha^2\{g(ax, bt)\} = \frac{1}{a^\alpha b^\alpha} k_\alpha\left(\frac{p}{a}, \frac{q}{b}\right),$$

where a, b are constants.

Proof. $A_\alpha^2\{g(ax, bt)\} = \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px + qt)^\alpha) g(ax, bt) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha.$

By letting $u = ax, v = bt$ we get:

$$A_\alpha^2\{g(ax)\} = \frac{1}{a^\alpha b^\alpha} \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha\left(-\left(\frac{p}{a}u + \frac{q}{b}v\right)^\alpha\right) g(u, v) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha = \frac{1}{a^\alpha b^\alpha} k_\alpha\left(\frac{p}{a}, \frac{q}{b}\right).$$

\square

4.3 Shifting property

Theorem 4.3. If $A_\alpha^2\{g(x, t)\} = k_\alpha(p, q)$, then $A_\alpha^2\{E_\alpha(-ax - bt)^\alpha g(x, t)\} = k_\alpha(p + a, q + b)$, where a, b are constants.

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} A_\alpha\{E_\alpha(-(ax + bt)^\alpha) g(x, y)\} &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px + qt)^\alpha) \\ &E_\alpha(-(ax + bt)^\alpha) g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha. \end{aligned}$$

By using the following property of the Mittag-Leffler function,

$$E_\alpha(-(px + qt)^\alpha) E_\alpha(-(ax + by)^\alpha) = E_\alpha(-((p + a)x + (q + b)t)^\alpha)$$

we get:

$$\begin{aligned} A_\alpha^2\{E_\alpha(-ax - bt)^\alpha g(x, t)\} &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-((p + a)x + (q + b)t)^\alpha) g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= k_\alpha(p + a, q + b) \end{aligned}$$

\square

4.4 Multiplication by $x^\alpha t^\alpha$

Theorem 4.4. If $A_\alpha^2 \{g(x, t)\} = k_\alpha(p, q)$, then $A_\alpha^2 (x^\alpha t^\alpha g(x, t)) = \frac{1}{pq} D_p^\alpha D_q^\alpha (pq k_\alpha(p, q))$.

Proof. We have

$$\begin{aligned} A_\alpha^2 (x^\alpha t^\alpha g(x, t)) &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px+qt)^\alpha) x^\alpha t^\alpha g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty D_p^\alpha D_q^\alpha [E_\alpha(-(px+qt)^\alpha)] g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{pq} D_p^\alpha D_q^\alpha \left[\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px+qt)^\alpha) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{pq} D_p^\alpha D_q^\alpha (pq k_\alpha(p, q)). \end{aligned}$$

□

4.5 Fractional double Aboodh transform of some fractional partial derivatives

Theorem 4.5. The fractional double Aboodh transform of fractional partial derivative respect to x is given by

$$A_\alpha^2 \left(\frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial x^\alpha} g(x, t) \right) = p^\alpha K_\alpha(p, q) - \frac{(1+\alpha)}{p} K_\alpha(0, q).$$

Proof. By applying Fractional integration by part formula with respect to x , we get:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(qt)^\alpha) \left[(1+\alpha) g(x, t) E_\alpha(-(px)^\alpha) \Big|_0^\infty - \int_0^\infty D_x^\alpha E_\alpha(-(px)^\alpha) g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha \right] (dt)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty -(1+\alpha) g(0, t) (dt)^\alpha + p^\alpha \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(qt)^\alpha) E_\alpha(-(px)^\alpha) g(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= -\frac{(1+\alpha)K_\alpha(0, q)}{p} + p^\alpha A_\alpha^2 (g(x, t)) \\ &= p^\alpha K_\alpha(p, q) - \frac{(1+\alpha)}{p} K_\alpha(0, q). \end{aligned}$$

□

Theorem 4.6. The fractional double Aboodh transform of fractional partial derivative respect to t is given by:

$$A_\alpha^2 \left(\frac{\partial^\alpha}{\partial t^\alpha} g(x, t) \right) = q^\alpha K_\alpha(p, q) - \frac{(1+\alpha)}{q} K_\alpha(p, 0).$$

Proof. Similar to that of theorem 4.5.

□

Theorem 4.7. The fractional double Aboodh transform of a mixed fractional partial derivative is given by:

$$A_\alpha^2 \left[\frac{\partial^{2\alpha}}{\partial x^\alpha \partial t^\alpha} g(x, t) \right] = (pq)^\alpha K_\alpha(p, q) - \frac{p^\alpha}{q} (\alpha!) K_\alpha(p, 0) - \frac{q^\alpha}{p} (\alpha!) K_\alpha(0, q) + \frac{1}{pq} (\alpha!)^2 g(0, 0)$$

Proof. Proof: Immediate by theorems 4.5 and 4.6.

□

Remark 4.1. All results above are suitable for double Aboodh transform when $\alpha = 1$.

5 Convolution Theorem of Fractional Double Aboodh Transform

Proposition 5.1. The double convolution of order α of functions $f(x, t)$ and $g(x, t)$ can be defined by the expression:

$$(f(x, t) **_\alpha g(x, t)) = \int_0^x \int_0^t f(x-z, t-w) g(z, w) (dz)^\alpha (dw)^\alpha. \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the fractional Aboodh transform of (11) is given by:

$$A_\alpha^2 \{f(x, t) **_\alpha g(x, t)\} = pq A_\alpha^2 \{f(x, t)\} A_\alpha^2 \{g(x, t)\}$$

Proof. We have

$$A_\alpha^2 \{f(x, t) * *_{\alpha} g(x, t)\} = \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px + pt)^\alpha) \left[\int_0^x \int_0^t f(x-z, t-w) g(z, w) (dz)^\alpha (dw)^\alpha \right] (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \tag{12}$$

By letting $u = x - z, v = t - w$ and taking the limit from zero to infinity, (12) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \left[\begin{aligned} &E_\alpha(-(p(u+z))^\alpha) E_\alpha(-(q(v+w))^\alpha) \\ &\left(\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(u, v) g(z, w) (dz)^\alpha (dw)^\alpha \right) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \end{aligned} \right] \\ &= \left[\begin{aligned} &\left(\frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-pz)^\alpha E_\alpha(-qw)^\alpha g(z, w) (dz)^\alpha (dw)^\alpha \right) \\ &\times \left(\int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-pu)^\alpha E_\alpha(-qv)^\alpha f(u, v) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \right) \end{aligned} \right] \\ &= pq A_\alpha^2 \{f(x, t)\} A_\alpha^2 \{g(x, t)\} \end{aligned}$$

□

6 Inversion formula of fractional double Aboodh transform

Definition 6.1 ([17]). The Dirac's distribution $\delta_\alpha(x, t)$ of order α , where $\alpha \in (0, 1)$ is defined by:

$$\int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} f(x, t) \delta_\alpha(x-a, t-b) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha = \alpha^2 f(a, b). \tag{12}$$

Example 6.1. The fractional double Aboodh transform of $\delta_\alpha(x-a, t-b)$ can be calculated as following:

$$\begin{aligned} A_\alpha^2 \{\delta_\alpha(x-a, t-b)\} &= \frac{1}{p} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-(px+qt)^\alpha) \delta_\alpha(x-a, t-b) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{\alpha}{pq} E_\alpha(-(pa+qb)^\alpha). \end{aligned}$$

In particular,

$$A_\alpha^2 \{\delta_\alpha(x, t)\} = \frac{\alpha}{pq}.$$

The following Lemma clarify the relation between $\delta_\alpha(x, t)$ and $E_\alpha(x+t)^\alpha$, this Lemma helps us to prove inversion theorem that we will consider later.

Lemma 6.1 ([17]). The following formula holds

$$\frac{\alpha^2}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} E_\alpha(i(-ux)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i(-wt)^\alpha) (du)^\alpha (dw)^\alpha = \delta_\alpha(x, t). \tag{13}$$

Where μ_α , satisfy $E_\alpha(i(\mu_\alpha)^\alpha) = 1$, and called the period of the complex-valued Mittag-leffer function.

Proof. We test that (13) is consistent with

$$\int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} E_\alpha(i(ux)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i(wt)^\alpha) \delta_\alpha(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha = \alpha^2. \tag{14}$$

By substituting (13), in (14), we get:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha^2 &= \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha E_\alpha(i(ux)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i(wt)^\alpha) \frac{\alpha^2}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} E_\alpha(i(-vx)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i(-st)^\alpha) (dv)^\alpha (ds)^\alpha \\ &= \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \frac{\alpha^2}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} E_\alpha(i((u-v)x)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i((w-s)t)^\alpha) (dv)^\alpha (ds)^\alpha \\ &= \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \frac{\alpha^2}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} E_\alpha(i(xp)^\alpha) E_\alpha(i(qt)^\alpha) (dp)^\alpha (dq)^\alpha \\ &= \int_{\Re} \int_{\Re} \delta_\alpha(x, t) (dx)^\alpha (dt)^\alpha \\ &= \alpha^2. \end{aligned}$$

□

7 Inversion Theorem of Fractional Double Aboodh Transform

Theorem 7.1. The inverse of the Fractional double Aboodh transform (9) is defined as:

$$f(x, t) = \frac{1}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} pq E_\alpha(px)^\alpha E_\alpha(qt)^\alpha k(p, q) (dp)^\alpha (dq)^\alpha \quad (15)$$

Proof. By substituting (15) into (9) and using (13) and (14) we get:

$$\begin{aligned} f(x, t) &= \frac{1}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} pq E_\alpha(px)^\alpha E_\alpha(qt)^\alpha (dp)^\alpha (dq)^\alpha \\ &\quad \frac{1}{pq} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty E_\alpha(-pu)^\alpha E_\alpha(-qv)^\alpha f(u, v) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty f(u, v) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \\ &\quad \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} \int_{-i\infty}^{i\infty} E_\alpha(p(x-u))^\alpha E_\alpha(q(t-v))^\alpha (dp)^\alpha (dq)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}} \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{(\mu_\alpha)^{2\alpha}}{\alpha^2} f(u, v) \delta_\alpha(u-x, v-t) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \\ &= \int_0^\infty \int_0^\infty \frac{1}{\alpha^2} f(u, v) \delta_\alpha(u-x, v-t) (du)^\alpha (dv)^\alpha \\ &= \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \cdot \alpha^2 f(x, t) = f(x, t). \end{aligned}$$

□

8 Conclusion

In this paper, we introduce the fractional double Aboodh transform and its inverse. Several theorems and properties of fractional double Aboodh transform have been discussed and proved. Our results are consistent with Aboodh transform when $\alpha = 1$.

References

- [1] Khalaf R.F. and Belgacem F.B.M., Extraction of the Laplace, Fourier, and Mellin Transforms from the Sumudu transform, AIP Proceedings, 1637, 1426 (2014)
- [2] Khan Z.H., and Khan W.A., Natural transform-properties and applications, NUST Journal of Engineering Sciences, 1(2008) 127-133
- [3] Shah K., Junaid M. and Ali N., Extraction of Laplace, Sumudu, Fourier and Mellin Transform from the Natural transform, J. Appl. Environ. Biol. Sci., 5(9) (2015) 108-115
- [4] Thakur, A. K. and Panda, S. " Some Properties of Triple Laplace Transform", Journal of Mathematics and Computer Applications Research (JMCAR), 2250-2408, (2015).
- [5] Belgacem F.B.M. and Karaballi A.A., Sumudu transform fundamental properties investigations and applications, Journal of applied mathematics and stochastic analysis, (2006)
- [6] Kili'eman A. A., Eltayeb H. and Atan K.A.M., A note on the comparison between Laplace and Sumudu transforms, Bull Iranian Math Soc, 37 (2011) 131-141
- [7] Khalid Suliman Aboodh, "The New Integral Transform" Aboodh Transform "Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics ISSN 0973-1768 Volume 9, Number 1 (2013), pp. 35-43.
- [8] Mohand, M, Khalid Suliman Aboodh, & Abdelbagy, A. On the Solution of Ordinary Differential Equation with Variable Coefficients using Aboodh Transform, Advances in Theoretical and Applied Mathematics ISSN 0973-4554 Volume 11, Number 4 (2016), pp. 383-389.
- [9] H. M. Baskonus, H. Bulut and Y. Pandir, The natural transform decomposition method for linear and nonlinear partial differential equations, Math. Engineer. Scie. Aerospace., 5 (1) (2014), 111-126.
- [10] S. Alfaqeh, T. Ozis First Aboodh Transform of Fractional Order and Its Properties International Journal of Progressive Sciences and Technologies (IJPSAT) (in process).
- [11] I. Podlubny, Fractional differential equations: an introduction to fractional derivatives, fractional differential equations, to methods of their solution and some of their applications, Vol. 198 (Academic press, 1998).
- [12] G. Jumarie, Table of some basic fractional calculus formulae derived from a modified Riemann–Liouville derivative for non-differentiable functions, Appl. Math. Lett. 22(2009)378–385.
- [13] R. Hilfer, Applications of fractional calculus in physics (World Scientific, 2000).
- [14]. K. Oldham and J. Spanier, The fractional calculus: Theory and applications of differentiation and integration to arbitrary order (Academic Press, New York, 1974).

- [15] Mittag-leffler, M.G., Sur la nouvelle fonction $() a E x$, Comptes Rendus AcadSci. Paris (Ser. II) 137(1903), 554-558.
- [16] K.S. Aboodh , R.A. Farah , I.A. Almardy and F.A. ALmostafa Solution of Partial Integro-Differential Equations by using Aboodh and Double Aboodh Transform Methods, Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics. ISSN 0973-1768 Volume 13, Number 8 (2017), pp. 4347-4360.
- [17] Guy Jumarie Laplace's transform of fractional order via the Mittag–Leffler function and modified Riemann–Liouville derivative

The L^AT_EX class for this article is Provided
for **ONLINE MATHEMATICS** by
Hend Dawood and Yasser Dawood
© 2018–2019 All Rights Reserved

Copyright © 2019, the author(s); licensee Online Mathematics, Infinity Bees.
This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>).
